

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHYSICAL QUALITY OF WRESTLERS INCREASE THE LEVEL

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Annotation

The development of the physical qualities of wrestlers in this proverb

The problem of increasing the level is studied

Key words

Physical quality, physical development, sports, style, training, physical fitness

To achieve high stable results, it is necessary to be comprehensively developed. All physical qualities are organically interconnected: the improvement of some contributes to the better manifestation of others. For example, you cannot successfully develop speed without increasing strength. The same wrestler, all other things being equal, will make a throw faster with an opponent who is smaller in weight, since when making a throw with a heavier opponent, a large expenditure of physical strength will be required. Therefore, the stronger the wrestler is, the better he will be able to show the quality of speed.

Strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility are developed directly in wrestling classes, as well as through the use of various general developmental exercises and exercises from other sports.

But not all general developmental exercises equally contribute to the development of physical qualities necessary for a wrestler. Of all their diversity, only those that contribute more to specialization in wrestling should be used. The wrestler performs exercises aimed at developing physical qualities during morning exercises, in wrestling classes and in specially organized physical training classes.

In a weekly training cycle, each day has its own main focus, i.e. when the main focus is mainly on the development of some physical quality or group of qualities. Purposeful physical training of a wrestler takes place throughout the sports year. Depending on the periods and stages of training, the means aimed at developing physical qualities are used in different ways. So in the main period, the proportion of general developmental exercises is less than in the preparatory and transitional periods. At the same time, in the main period, at the

stage of preliminary preparation for competitions, in the post-competition stage, general developmental exercises and exercises from other sports are used to a greater extent than at the stage of preparation for competitions.

Control exercises are used to check the level of development of physical qualities of wrestlers. To improve the physical qualities of wrestlers, methods of planning and controlling training loadings are developed to develop the physical qualities of wrestlers, and are tested in the experience. In young wrestlers, accurate results were obtained on the development of their physical qualities. Materials from scientific research work are used in the annual training program of the wrestling training.

The main cases that are issued :

- Develop the physical qualities that are used in wrestling training.
- The development of a tool and more effective techniques used in the development of special power qualities in wrestlers through normalised loadings.
- Increase the level of development of important physical qualities of wrestlers;

Among the practical qualities in the special literature is understood the activity of the character and its level, the ability to have a muscular tension that invades the resistance of mechanical and biomechanical forces, resists the activity of movement, and it is expressed in the phrase "Power possibility".

Strength ability is categorized into types such as personal strength, agility strength, and strength endurance. The upper period of its rate of development is noticeable in adolescents from 13-14 years and young people from 16-18 years.

It is required to develop a certain level of strength so that those involved can perform the exercise of climbing and surpassing labyrinth obstacles.

The group of muscles that worked when hanging with force and walking through the maze with a support for the chest also work in performing exercises of pulling on the turn, bending and writing the hand from the elbow in a lying position, bending and writing the hand with a support. To another, in physical education classes, exercises performed using the weight of the torso are of great importance in the development of muscle strength. The leading method of training the quality of speed is considered to be rapid repetition training, and the movement being practiced is repeated many times at the highest speed. During the repetition of the exercise, the first symptoms of slowing down of movement appear, as soon as it is felt, the exercise is required to be stopped

immediately. It has been proven that the continuation of this condition leads to the development of endurance.

By analyzing the sources of literature, we came to the opinion that most authors offer only a maximum speed running exercise for a short distance of 20 to 60 meters in order to educate the quality of speed. At the same time, each author recommends his programs, in which the number of repetitions, series and rest intervals differ from each other.

Scientists confirm that while special durability is considered a multi-factor concept from the point of view of pedagogy, the degree of its development is inextricably linked with a number of other factors, such as overall durability, speed quality and mastery in terms of technique.

General durability serves as the basis for the upbringing of various manifestations of special durability, therefore, the work associated with the development of general durability, in relation to the development of special durability, should be planned earlier.

Power Development

The strength of a wrestler is the ability to overcome the opponent's resistance or counteract it by straining muscles. The manifestation of strength depends on the physiological diameter, the structure of the muscles and the characteristics of the course of nervous processes. The strength of the action on the opponent also largely depends on the strong-willed qualities of the wrestler, his ability to mobilize himself, on how perfect and rational his technique is, what is the lever arm when grabbing, how skillfully he combines his efforts with the efforts of the opponent, uses the weight of the body and observes other patterns of technical actions (see "Biomechanical patterns technical actions").

It is known that muscle strength during inhalation, exhalation and breath retention manifests itself in different ways: the greatest efforts can be made at the moment of holding the breath and exhaling. In wrestling, the intensity and nature of muscle tension are constantly changing: static and dynamic muscle efforts take place here, moments of extreme tension are replaced by short pauses of relative relaxation, etc. During the fight, the wrestler has to perform power movements and actions in a wide variety of situations, body positions, with fresh strength and against a background of great fatigue.

Conducting techniques (counter-techniques) and resisting the actions of the enemy require a high level of strength development of each of the muscle groups. In most cases, the force in the fight is explosive, i.e. it manifests itself in

sharp movements performed with maximum speed. All these features are reflected in the methods and means of developing strength.

One of the most effective means of developing strength is general developmental and special exercises with weights. As a burden, they are used: the participant's own body weight, partner, wrestling dummy (bag), barbell, kettlebells, dumbbells, stuffed balls, blocks, expander, rubber shock absorbers and other means. To develop the strength of a wrestler, an effective means is to perform individual techniques and fights with partners with greater strength or greater weight. The overcoming method takes the leading place in the struggle. A good effect is provided by a combination of overcoming, yielding and isometric methods of strength development.

Most authors recommend using a run in one run of different norms to develop overall endurance. According to a group of authors, the use of moderate, moderately intense running makes changes that are not high in the importance of developing endurance. Therefore, considering that the time is limited, they recommend replacing the use of repeated running with moderate, one-time running in turn. Most authors' studies confirm that the chances of developing resilience are high in adolescents and suggest that it focuses on developing that quality. There is an opinion that it will be necessary to develop a mechanism that generates primary power, so this will give physical loads the opportunity to increase the ability to work in moderate and large-intensity zones. As such, increasing aerobic production to a higher level improves the body's ability to recover, in turn creating favorable conditions for improving aerobic capacity .

Referring to the state educational standard and curriculum analysis of general secondary education, many times jumping exercises have been given more place in argamchi in the development of general endurance. It is justified that these exercises should be performed at the end of the main part of the lesson, after mastering new movement activities or after exercises in which speed and strength are required. National recommended the use of action games in the development of overall durability, and it consisted of activities that were performed with intensity in a short period of time. The use of National Action Games develops overall endurance and is characterized by increasing the useful density of training. Running physical exercises in all physical education classes contribute to the development of endurance and working capacity. During the preparatory period, exercises performed with a force of a cyclic nature using a standard-continuous technique are performed for two months (at the end of the gymnastics lesson, 10-15min. during) by performing a.A. Kharlampiev had

achieved a 6.4% increase in endurance. It is known that in exercises performed with a 90% intensity, the duration of a one-time load (1m) for the development of speed-endurance is 50-80 SEC, the number of repetitions is 5-8 times, the length of the rest interval is 2-3 min. is considered to consist of.

One of the generally accepted ways to train strength and endurance is a "repeated strain". To develop strength and endurance, the intensity of exercises should correspond to 20-50% of the maximum strength, while the exercises themselves are performed until complete fatigue. The volume of loading is selected taking into account the symptoms of the exact expression of exhaustion and depending on their ability to perform 15-30 times, the second half of the main part of the training is entered in the form of a task complex at the "station".

The problem of training human endurance has been sufficiently studied, but in our eyes we must admit that this quality has an important advantage in learning in order to train struggling young people.

Endurance is characterized as the duration of the period of maintenance of the body's working capacity and the degree of its resistance, to withstand the influence of fatigue or negative factors of the external environment.

In recent years, resilience and its types have been expressed as a holistic concept consisting of sums. For example: strength endurance, general and special endurance, speed endurance.

One can also find such points in the literature: special durability is also a polymorphic (multi-shaped) quality. Its development depends on the sum of such as a number of components: general durability, speed, special, strength, which somehow react to different interaction with each other and the main quality. Special durability is a synthesis of two main physical qualities - speed and durability.

These two qualities are in excellent communication with a special force, which is carried out as the sports skill grows. Special durability is also approached by the authors from approximately such a point of view. They believe that speed should be demonstrated in the most responsible period of the race, when the athlete is most tired, and endurance throughout the race.

It has been found that the issues of the development of special strength of wrestlers have made young teenagers more physically prepared for entering the wrestling specialty, using training tools aimed at endurance, strength, agility and other physical qualities in every possible way. It is argued that during the initial sports training period, 50 percent of the total training time should be focused on

endurance training, 25 percent on speed training and 25 percent on strength training.

The aerobic and anaerobic capabilities of the body depend on the intensity and duration of the exercise, the number of repetitions and the intervals of rest .

Strength training in athletes has been investigated. Although it is of great importance in the upbringing of young people from the scientific and methodological side of the work, it is not entirely suitable for solving the problem of special power in general.

D.L.Examination work done by Rudman showed that incorporating the circular training style into athletics, in the form of running, play and competition, enhanced special strength, as well as other physical qualities. In several other studies it has been shown that a positive result can also be achieved in a short repeated interval of rest to effectively increase overall endurance.

In raising special strength in children and adolescents, a slow and scientific approach is needed, taking into account the lack of functional training of the organism, and it has been shown that it is necessary to educate more qualities of agility during this age.

According to some scientists, being very careful in the development of Special Forces confirms that general physical training in young people is not fully given . Each teacher should not forget that the intensity of the exercises depends on the individual and the training of the student. While 75-80% of the maximum intensity in newly engaged children is one limit, in well-trained athletes it is another.

Fatigue, which is formed in schoolchildren, is only possible within a short time due to the fact that it is in a small stagnation to large triggers of the nervous system.

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